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TEACHING ON EMPTY: BURNOUT CHALLENGES IN ELT CLASSROOMS

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to the issue of professional exhaustion—burnout—among English language teachers. It discusses the causes of burnout, its impact on the educational process, and strategies to mitigate it. Based on academic studies, the authors analyze the unique aspects of burnout in the context of ELT (English Language Teaching). The results demonstrate the necessity of enhancing teachers' psychological support, boosting their confidence, and increasing motivation.

Key words: Burnout, ELT, causes of exhaustion, motivation, teacher well-being, professional development.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ingliz tili o'qituvchilari orasida uchraydigan kasbiy charchoq – burn out (ruhiy-psixologik toliqish) muammosiga bag'ishlangan. Unda burn outning sabablari, uning ta'lim jarayoniga ta'siri va uni kamaytirish strategiyalari muhokama qilingan. Akademik tadqiqotlar asosida mualliflar ingliz tilini o'qitishda (ELT) burn out holatining o'ziga xos jihatlari tahlil qilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari o'qituvchilarga psixologik yordamni kuchaytirish, ularning ishonchini oshirish va motivatsiyasini rag'batlantirish zarurligini ko'rsatmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: burn out, ELT, charchoq sabablari, motivatsiya, o'qituvchi farovonligi, kasbiy rivojlanish.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена проблеме профессионального выгорания (burnout) среди преподавателей английского языка. В ней рассматриваются причины выгорания, его влияние на образовательный процесс, а также стратегии его предотвращения. На основе научных исследований авторы анализируют специфические аспекты выгорания в контексте преподавания английского языка (ELT). Результаты подчёркивают необходимость усиления психологической поддержки учителей, повышения их уверенности в себе и мотивации.

Ключевые слова: выгорание, ELT, причины усталости, мотивация, благополучие учителя, профессиональное развитие.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the issue of teacher burnout has emerged as a significant concern, particularly within the domain of English Language Teaching (ELT). Teaching in ELT classrooms often demands not only linguistic expertise but also emotional resilience, classroom management skills, and the ability to adapt to diverse student needs. As a result, many ELT teachers experience what is commonly termed as “teaching on empty”—continuing their professional responsibilities despite feeling physically exhausted, emotionally drained, and mentally disengaged. This article explores the root causes of burnout among ELT professionals, examines its impact on both educators and learners, and proposes strategies for alleviating this growing problem.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Causes of Burnout in ELT Classrooms. Several factors contribute to burnout among ELT teachers. According to Özdemir (2015), a primary source of burnout is the high emotional and cognitive load placed on teachers due to diverse learner needs and continuous performance demands. Additionally, Fathi, Derakhshan, and Torabi (2024) highlight that low self-efficacy—a teacher's belief in their ability to manage and succeed in teaching tasks—correlates strongly with higher burnout levels. Other contributors include inadequate administrative support, lack of professional development opportunities, oversized classrooms, and limited resources. Shirazizadeh, Derakhshan, and Zhaleh (2022) add that chronic stress, caused by unrealistic expectations and job insecurity, exacerbates emotional exhaustion. Teachers often report feeling unappreciated and undervalued, which reduces motivation and increases the risk of psychological withdrawal from teaching duties.

Burnout in ELT classrooms is often the result of a combination of demanding conditions that place significant emotional and physical strain on teachers. Overcrowded classrooms, often with 20–25 students, make it difficult to manage behavior and provide individualized support. Excessive workloads—such as lesson planning, grading, and administrative paperwork—frequently extend beyond teaching hours, leaving little time for rest. Compounding this are low salaries and financial insecurity, which are common in many developing countries and private institutions, where teachers may struggle to meet basic living costs. A lack of professional development opportunities can lead to feelings of stagnation and reduced motivation, especially in remote or under-resourced areas. Additionally, teachers often face limited access to up-to-date teaching materials and must rely on personal resources to fill the gap. The emotional labor involved in managing unmotivated or disruptive students, while maintaining a positive classroom environment, further contributes to exhaustion. In multicultural classrooms, cultural misunderstandings and communication barriers may increase stress levels. Job insecurity due to short-term contracts or freelance arrangements adds another layer of anxiety, making teachers feel undervalued and unsupported in their professional roles. Together, these factors create a high-risk environment for burnout in ELT contexts.

Why burnout is a serious issue in ELT contexts. Burnout in ELT classrooms presents unique challenges. Language learning environments require dynamic and interactive teaching methods. Emotional disengagement from the teacher can significantly hinder students' motivation and participation. As Zhaleh, Derakhshan, and Fathi (2022) explain, burnout negatively affects teachers' instructional clarity and feedback ability—both of which are essential for language acquisition. Moreover, English language teachers frequently work in multilingual or multicultural classrooms, which demands additional emotional labor. According to Taxer and Frenzel (2021), the necessity to perform emotional labor—displaying positive emotions even when one feels distressed—can lead to surface acting, which is closely linked with higher burnout rates. These conditions are often intensified in foreign contexts where English is not the native language, increasing cultural pressures and expectations on teachers.

Impacts on teachers and students. The effects of burnout are not limited to the teachers themselves. Emotionally exhausted educators tend to exhibit lower levels of enthusiasm, less creativity, and reduced willingness to adapt or innovate in the classroom. Pishghadam and Khajavy (2024) emphasize that burnout among EFL teachers leads to decreased well-being and negatively affects students' academic performance and classroom morale. When teachers are burned out, students may receive less constructive feedback and feel a lack of engagement from their instructors. This disengagement can demotivate students and hinder their language development. Additionally, high teacher turnover rates due to burnout disrupt learning continuity and affect the overall quality of education (Kustati & Nasution, 2021).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Strategies for preventing and managing burnout. Addressing teacher burnout requires a multi-faceted approach involving personal, institutional, and systemic strategies. At the personal level, enhancing teachers' self-efficacy through professional development workshops, peer mentoring, and reflective teaching practices can build resilience (Fathi et al., 2024). Schools and institutions must recognize the importance of emotional support structures such as counseling services and teacher support groups. From an administrative perspective, creating manageable workloads, reducing class sizes, and offering regular breaks or mental health days can significantly alleviate burnout.

According to Kasalak and Dağyar (2022), teacher feedback-ability improves with reduced stress and better emotional regulation. Motivational programs that recognize teacher contributions, offer career advancement opportunities, and foster a sense of belonging also play an essential role. As Kustati and Nasution (2021) suggest, motivation can serve as a powerful buffer against the pressures of daily teaching tasks. In addition, ensuring fair and stable contracts with adequate pay and benefits can reduce financial stress and increase job satisfaction. Government policies should promote teacher well-being by investing in infrastructure, updating teaching materials, and integrating teacher voices into decision-making processes. Cross-cultural training for teachers in diverse classrooms can help prevent misunderstandings and reduce emotional tension, especially in international settings. Ultimately, a holistic and sustained effort from all stakeholders—teachers, institutions, and policy-makers—is needed to create a teaching environment that nurtures rather than depletes educators.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Burnout among ELT teachers is typically linked to high workloads, limited resources, low social recognition, and constant stress—all of which can significantly hinder their ability to perform effectively in the classroom. This chronic strain not only affects teachers' well-being but also reduces students' interest in lessons and nega-

tively impacts overall learning outcomes, as disengaged and emotionally exhausted teachers may struggle to maintain classroom enthusiasm and instructional quality. Therefore, promoting mental health among teachers through supportive policies, access to counseling services, and professional development opportunities plays a crucial role in mitigating burnout and fostering a more productive and positive educational environment.

The analysis shows that burnout can be not only a personal issue but also a source of professional crisis for teachers. To reduce this issue, teachers need continuous methodological assistance, psychological support, and balanced workloads. As Fathi et al. (2024) emphasize, a teacher's self-efficacy has a strong influence on burnout. Similarly, according to Taxer and Frenzel (2021), emotional labor is one of the main factors contributing to burnout.

CONCLUSION

Burnout among ELT professionals is a complex issue that affects not only the well-being of teachers but also the quality of education that learners receive. Recognizing the symptoms of burnout and implementing effective interventions can ensure more sustainable and rewarding teaching environments. By fostering self-efficacy, providing emotional and institutional support, and promoting motivation, ELT institutions can help educators avoid “teaching on empty” and instead teach with renewed energy and purpose.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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